

Cultural identity of Environmental Sustainability in Iranian vernacular architecture

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Introduction

In today's modern world, where technology and industry are advancing and separating humans from the life they had in the past, two factors are very important. sustainability in relation to energy preservation, and the sense of belonging in architecture. To conserve energy in buildings, various methods can be used, one of which is adhering to the principles of vernacular architecture. In the past, Iranians paid great attention to climate conditions and to maintaining and providing the energy they needed naturally. The use of vernacular architectural principles gives people a sense of belonging. Today, most buildings follow a modern architectural style, usually characterized by cold, repetitive colors and materials such as concrete. Although they may appear aesthetically pleasing at first, over time, living in such spaces creates a sense of alienation from the environment. Throughout their lives, people often feel nostalgic for the past and this is exactly the point where humans long to experience an architecture that reflects their identity and allows them to feel a true sense of belonging.

Abstract

Sustainability is one of the most important discussions in countries, the factors that cause sustainable architecture are many, but one of them is vernacular architecture, which causes sustainability through the orientation of the building itself, the type of materials, the color of the building, construction strategies, and the climate plays a fundamental role in the vernacular architecture and causes the formation of vernacular architecture, but one of the influential factors in the formation of vernacular architecture is its people. There are regions whose habits, behaviors, and culture are reflected in the buildings, and the vernacular architecture is a reflection of the climate and the people. In today's world, where technology is rapidly advancing and people are becoming increasingly disconnected from their past, a sense of emptiness and loss of belonging has emerged. Adapted vernacular architecture, redesigned to meet modern needs and climates, can effectively respond to this need and serve as a means of restoring identity and promoting sustainability in contemporary architecture.

Keywords: Indigenous Architecture – Sustainability – Sense of Belonging – Iranian Architecture – Climate

Hypothesis and Questions

Hypothesis: Using the principles of vernacular architecture to create sustainability in architecture and a sense of belonging.

Question 1: How do the principles of vernacular architecture create sustainability and are they applicable in today's world?

Question 2: How can vernacular architecture create a sense of belonging, and why is this sense important in today's architecture?

Research Background

A study conducted by Masoud Rezaei et al. (2014): indicates that architecture and construction can either pose threats to the environment or, if designed properly and based on the climatic and cultural factors of each region, contribute to energy conservation and environmental sustainability. The research emphasizes that Iranian vernacular architecture, with its thousands of years of history, has been shaped through the experiences of its inhabitants and their understanding of the climate and culture of each area. The native builders, who were often the residents themselves, carefully examined factors such as materials, climate conditions, building dimensions, types of roofs, verandas, and courtyards to utilize beneficial environmental elements while minimizing harmful ones. Findings from this study demonstrate that vernacular rural architecture serves as a scientific and practical model of sustainable architecture, which can help reduce energy consumption and construction costs in modern architectural design.

The study by Fatemeh Hajhasan and Ansieh Ghorbaninia (2011): states that vernacular architecture has been functional in every period of history. Although it has faced various transformations over time, it has preserved its identity, as it reflects the customs, traditions, and beliefs of the people of each region. Therefore, it can be regarded as the cultural identity or passport of a nation. In the past, the goal of vernacular architecture was to create an environment that was continuously in harmony with the people's culture and way of life; however, in today's world, architecture often serves only mechanical and functional needs, resulting in a rigid and impersonal relationship between humans and their built environment.

Mohammad Mangali and Mohsen Keshavarz (2024): This study investigated and compared the internal thermal comfort level (PMV) of four handmade monuments of the Meymand World Heritage Site and four mountain stone buildings of Rayseh village under similar climatic conditions. The results showed that in winter, Meymand handmade buildings are closer to the neutral comfort level and their internal temperature is about 5.44 degrees Celsius warmer than the spinning houses, which indicates better thermal comfort and reduced energy consumption. The comfort function of vernacular buildings can help to complete the understanding of ancient architectural patterns.

Maryam Armaghan & Yousef Gorji Mahlahbani Summer (2009): The sustainable architecture approach requires a suitable local context, but the traditional policies that have led to the creation of shelters that have been sustainable over the centuries are not able to meet the needs and resources of the present time. Paying attention to vernacular characteristics is noteworthy from two aspects: one, creating a suitable platform for the formation of sustainable architecture, and the other, the use of repeatable values of vernacular architecture, in the architectural process.

Elham Iraj (Summer 2020): The interaction between vernacular architecture and green architecture is a deep and ancient one. Vernacular architecture is a dynamic form of architecture that harmonizes and adapts with the climatic, cultural, and natural characteristics of each region. Today, with the increase in construction, less attention is paid to the design context, which often results in designs that are incompatible with their surroundings both climatically and culturally.

Ali Javan Forouzandeh and Ghasem Motalebi Summer 2011: The sense of belonging is one of the important factors in evaluating the relationship between humans and the environment. The sense of belonging has two physical and social dimensions, which the results show that social belonging is superior to physical belonging. Belonging is rooted in the social interactions and relationship of the individual with others. Basically, human beings seek to respond to their needs in the environment, and if these positive needs are not met, they will not feel positive about the environment.

Sustainability in vernacular architecture of Iran

Sustainable Architecture: A sustainable building is a building that has the least incompatibility and contradiction with its surroundings and in a wider area with the world [1].

The goal of sustainability has been to improve the quality dimension and preserve the natural environment for the future needs of human beings. The term sustainability is used to describe a world in which both human and natural systems can survive for the foreseeable future [2].

Sustainable architecture can be achieved through the use of renewable materials, green walls, wind catchers, solar panels, and other methods—one of which is the application of vernacular architecture suited to the specific region. Despite its universal and fundamental principles that aim to preserve the Earth, sustainability encourages local approaches in order to develop practical and realistic solutions on one hand, and to support the diversity inherent in nature on the other. It emphasizes the well-known motto: Think globally, act locally [3].

Vernacular Architecture: In general, vernacular architecture can be defined as a form of architecture derived from environmental characteristics to meet human needs within a given setting. It evolves in harmony with the climate, environment, and culture of a region, based on extensive experience and traditional knowledge [4].

Vernacular or local architecture refers to a range of construction methods in which local materials, knowledge, labor, and traditions are used to meet the needs and desires of the local people. This architecture is born from the culture and the land, and therefore, evolves over time along with the culture [5].

Vernacular architecture means the architecture of the people, built by the people, and not for the people [6]. Vernacular architecture represents individual, environmental, historical, and cultural identity. The locals find themselves — along with all their desires and needs — reflected in the buildings constructed within and inspired by their own land [7].

Architecture is a collection of changes and transformations that have emerged based on human needs on Earth [8]. Vernacular or popular architecture is the natural and local architecture of a community. If these people migrate to another place, even if the new climatic conditions conflict with the characteristics of their original architecture, they generally carry their architecture with them. However, it usually takes some time for the original form of their architecture to adapt to the new conditions, and during this process, it often leads to the emergence of a new form of vernacular architecture that is derived from the characteristics of the previous style [9].

Iranian Vernacular Architecture

It can be stated that until about fifty years ago, and before the unrestricted entry of global architectural and urban planning culture into our country, ancient Iranians — in the simplest yet most intelligent way — made use of the blessings of their natural environment and harmonized their lives and houses with it. What has not yet been fully studied and has only been mentioned in scattered generalities is the world of thought in which ancient Iranians lived; a world that accepted transformations gradually and each day produced something new, integrating it with relative ease into daily life, both in the home and in the city [10].

The traditional form of the Iranian city was a perfect example of a healthy urban structure. Residents of the old neighborhoods could easily provide for all their daily and basic needs without the anxiety of traffic or long distances. A close look at the structure of traditional cities shows that every intervention in urban development was formed based on the real needs of citizens, not on the styles or personal preferences of designers — in other words, the growth of the city was completely organic. All gradual developments in the city were the result of citizens' needs for housing or other necessities, while always respecting their cultural and social values. Accordingly, one had to first enter the main street of the neighborhood, then pass through smaller alleys, after which came dead-ends leading to a Hashti (entrance vestibule). This spatial sequence allowed for strong social control and privacy within the urban fabric, as all paths ultimately ended at dead-ends where the main entrance of each house was located — reducing the chances of escape for strangers or intruders [12].

In the past, Iranian architecture was in harmony with the principles of sustainability. Traditional Iranian design paid a close attention to the natural form of the land and maintained harmony with it. The central courtyard and the introverted structure of the houses were reflections of the cultural values of the people. The pool of water located in the center of the courtyard helped to circulate air and separate the indoor space from the hot outdoor air. In such houses, there were summer and winter living areas: during summer, people used the rooms built on the northern side of the courtyard and facing south, to prevent direct sunlight from entering; for winter, the winter rooms were built on the southern side and faced north, allowing more sunlight and warmth inside. The colored windows in old Iranian houses not only prevented excessive heat from entering but also kept insects away due to their geometric patterns. When sunlight passed through these stained-glass windows, the colorful light patterns created a sense of peace and tranquility and also enhanced the aesthetic quality of the space.

The houses and windcatchers (Badgirs) in the city of Yazd have long contributed to sustainability and the conservation of energy. The light-colored facades of buildings in Yazd reflect sunlight, which is essential given the desert climate of the region. The narrow and winding alleys, along with the presence of Sabats (covered passages), create shade and facilitate air circulation throughout the urban fabric. Thick mud-brick walls were used in traditional houses to respond to the city's climate — characterized by extremely hot and dry summers and cold, dry winters. The windcatchers of Yazd function by directing warm air outward and allowing cooler air to flow inside, naturally cooling the interior spaces. These windcatchers are often polygonal in shape, enabling them to capture wind from multiple directions. Since the prevailing and desirable winds in Yazd usually blow from the north or northeast, the windcatchers are typically oriented toward these directions to maximize efficiency.

The traditional houses in the city of Gilan are among the most remarkable examples of vernacular architecture contributing to sustainability. Gilan has a humid climate, and therefore, houses were built elevated above the ground. The space beneath the house was supported by wooden stilts, which separated the floor from the ground surface. This technique prevented moisture and insects from entering the living space, while the airflow beneath the structure kept the floor dry. Due to the region's heavy rainfall, the roofs were designed with a steep slope and constructed from natural materials such as local wood and clay tiles. Another characteristic feature of Gilan's traditional houses is their large verandas (ivans), which allowed air to circulate and cooled the interior spaces. The orientation of the houses was aligned with the direction of the sea breeze, so that the openings and windows faced the prevailing wind. Since these houses were often built within natural landscapes, the trees surrounding them also contributed to energy efficiency by providing shade and cooling.

Another city that has sustainable vernacular architecture is Bushehr, which is located in the south of Iran and has a hot and humid climate. The houses are usually built facing the sea breeze, and local materials such as stone, gypsum, and palm wood are used in their construction. Thick walls are used to prevent humidity from penetrating inside. The facades are light-colored, and some have

cool tones to reflect sunlight and create a sense of coolness for the viewer. The city of Bushehr, like Yazd, has narrow and winding alleys that allow air to flow faster; however, unlike Yazd, central courtyards are not used in the houses. The presence of a pool in Bushehr increases humidity, which is why courtyards are avoided. The houses have verandas (ivans) that provide shade and coolness during the day, and it can be said that they have a natural ventilation system.

The city of Kermanshah is located in the west of Iran and has a temperate and mountainous climate. The local materials used in construction include clay, adobe, stone, and wood. The walls are thick to resist the cold weather. Houses are usually oriented toward the south to receive the maximum amount of sunlight. They are generally introverted, and small and few windows are used to prevent heat loss. These houses also have summer and winter living areas and a central courtyard, similar to those in Yazd.

Gilan's house

Bushehr's house

Wind catcher, Yazd

City	Climate	Materials	Design Features	Sustainability
Yazd	Hot and dry	Clay, mud	The central courtyard, summer and winter living areas, bright façade color, thick walls, sabbats, and narrow alleys	Wind catcher, introversion, central courtyard
Gilan	Moderate, humid	Palm tree, plaster, stone	Distance from ground level, porch and shading, sloping roof	Preventing soil moisture, using natural materials
Bushehr	Warm and humid	Wood of palm tree, plaster, stone	Cool façade paint, porches and shading, narrow alleys	Shading, use of natural materials, orientation in the direction of sea wire
Kermanshah	Temperate mountainous	Clay, stone, wood	Low openings, thick walls	Orientation to the south to create heat, the thick wall

				prevents the entry of cold in the winter and prevents the cold from leaving in the summer
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Sense of belonging and sense of place

The word “sense” in the Oxford Dictionary has three main meanings. First, it refers to one of the five senses. Second, it denotes a feeling, emotion, or affection—that is, a judgment formed after perceiving the meaning of an object in relation to oneself, which can be positive, appealing, or negative. Third, it signifies the ability to make judgments about an abstract matter. Ultimately, sense refers to the comprehensive or overall perception of an object by a human being. In the context of sense of place, however, the term primarily relates to emotion, affection, judgment, and the overall experience or the capacity of a place to evoke a particular feeling or sense of belonging in individuals [12].

From a phenomenological perspective, a place is more than an abstract location; it is a composite whole made up of real objects and things. A place serves as a context for activities and generally possesses a cognitive identity. It encompasses diverse social factors and carries a history that connects the past, present, and future [13].

The sense of belonging refers to a strong bond and an influential factor connecting the culture of people with a place and its constituent elements. This bond is positive, enhancing the depth of an individual’s interaction and engagement with the environment, and over time, its depth and scope increase [14].

Sociologists, and particularly anthropologists, have consistently emphasized that place, location, and territory are highly significant for people because they possess a strong capacity for identity formation. The sense of belonging to a place primarily involves being unique and distinctive, remaining stable and enduring, maintaining continuity, and feeling part of a community. In clearer terms, the definable and bounded nature of a place enables individuals to experience a sense of distinctiveness, stability, and social belonging, thereby providing the security and peace necessary for life [15].

Providing a complete definition of sense of place is challenging, as it is a subjective phenomenon. As Schultz argues, a place is a space that is first felt and then intertwined with memories. Therefore, it is through human experiences and memories that feelings toward a place—and, in common terms, the sense of place—are formed [16].

Based on their experiences of signs, meanings, and functions, individuals imagine a role for a place in their minds. This role is unique and distinct for each person, making the place significant and worthy of respect. A place fosters a sense of belonging and attachment because it enables social interactions and shared experiences among people [17].

It can be inferred that the sense of place gives rise to the sense of belonging, and in fact, the sense of belonging can be considered a subset of the sense of place. A place is first perceived through its spatial characteristics and objects. Then, after accepting the place and its associated cultures, an individual sees themselves as part of it. The resulting feelings of comfort and security lead to an emotional attachment to the place, and ultimately, to the development of a sense of belonging.

The sense of belonging in the vernacular architecture of Iran

Environmental and physical factors include characteristics that are also components of vernacular architectural culture. For example, the presence of historical buildings, the types of materials used, old streets and passageways, continuous façades, human-scale design, and consideration of climatic issues in design are all elements that create environmental distinctiveness and influence the sense of belonging to a place. All cultural components of vernacular architecture, due to their impact on the form and physical structure of the environment, can be considered shared between these two domains. The progression from exterior to interior in vernacular architecture should also be incorporated within the framework of cognitive-perceptual factors [18].

Ecologism leads to the formation of a sense of belonging to a place and space, and consequently, to the development of place identity. In this way, an ecologist approach results in a form of architecture rooted in both the human characteristics of the space and its environmental conditions [19].

In the past, humans lived in nature, and vernacular architecture was derived from and existed within it. People did not consider buildings as their true homes; rather, they saw nature as their primary dwelling. This is why traditional houses evoke a sense of belonging. In fact, the sense of belonging is rooted in the collection of memories that an individual has experienced in a place. Over time, as one nostalgically reflects on those periods, this emotional connection develops, leading to a sense of attachment to vernacular architecture or to the places where one previously lived.

Enhancing the Sense of Belonging in Contemporary Architecture

The sense of belonging to a place arises in individuals over time, shaped by the cultural, religious, and artistic characteristics of the space. In other words, this sense develops alongside the ornamentation present in a building and leaves a lasting impression on people's memories. For this

reason, being in spaces adorned with elements associated with Iranian architecture significantly influences each individual's perception of Iranian culture and fosters a sense of belonging [20].

Architecture and life are mirrors reflecting one another in their entirety [19].

Having a sense of belonging to a place, whether one has lived there or not, or is merely familiar with it, is crucial; otherwise, anything else can create feelings of emptiness and alienation toward the current environment. Even if a person did not grow up in Iran, or even if they grew up there but not in traditional houses, they can still experience a sense of belonging, as it can be transmitted indirectly and across generations. Today, architecture has moved toward minimalism, and the prevalence of cold and lifeless spaces can induce feelings of depression in individuals. Over time, architectural styles from the past may be revisited and utilized, but it is no longer feasible to replicate them exactly, as people's culture and the local climate may have changed. Therefore, a modified form of vernacular architecture should be employed—one that not only ensures sustainability but also prevents feelings of emptiness.

Conclusion

today, sustainability is the most important principle in architecture and globally, due to energy crises and issues such as global warming. Sustainability in architecture is highly significant and can have a major impact on energy conservation. Consequently, there are various methods to achieve sustainable architecture, and in this article, one such method—vernacular architecture—is examined.

Historically, architecture evolved through trial and error, in harmony with nature and local culture, with natural ventilation occurring organically. The principles of vernacular architecture that are still applicable today remain the same, but the climate and cultural context have changed. Therefore, vernacular architecture for the modern world must address both sustainability and contemporary cultural conditions.

Humans often develop a sense of belonging to a place. Iranian vernacular architecture can evoke this sense of belonging among Iranians, even if a traditional house belongs to a different city. In the near future, vernacular architecture could once again become popular among people, similar to the widespread appeal of minimalist architecture, because it promotes sustainability while fostering a sense of belonging. While minimalism has many supporters, the sense of belonging is a fundamental value in architecture. Spending time in cold, concrete spaces or areas with dull colors can lead to feelings of depression and nostalgia. Using modified vernacular architecture, adapted to contemporary culture, can reduce such feelings of melancholy and enhance emotional connection to the space.

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